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Biyaheng De-pedal: A Descriptive Phenomenological Study on the Commute Experience of Filipino Cyclists in Metro Manila in Association with Social Practice Theory

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Abstract

In 2021, Social Weather Stations reported the Philippines' Metro Manila with the highest ratio of bicycle ownership among households and the highest ratio of bicycle owners to car owners in the country. Through the lens of Social Practice Theory, the researchers used Materials, Meaning, and Competencies of Filipino cyclists in understanding the cyclists' overall commute experience in Metro Manila. This study discovers the purpose of Filipino cyclists in choosing their mode of transportation and explains their views on safety, practicality, accessibility, and implementation of policies. The researchers used descriptive phenomenological research design and gathered data via online interviews. The data was analyzed using Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis. Results show the overarching sub-themes with the three main themes based on the participants' responses: (1) Positive Synergy of Cycling, (2) Uncontrolled External Resources, and (3) User Managed Internal Resources. Cycling contains flexibility, efficiency, practicality, easy maintenance, and benefits health and environment. In addition, Filipino cyclists view their commute experience as a positive synergy especially for its practicality and its aid in health enhancement and environment refinement. Lastly, the advantages of cycling as a mode of transportation are the ease of management and the user managed internal resources. On the other hand, the disadvantages are the uncontrolled external resources including the ineffectiveness of cycling related policies and poor risk management.

Keywords: *bicycle, cyclists, commute experience, social practice theory*

Introduction

Commuting is part of the daily routine most people have whether one is a student or a worker. While the Philippines has a wide range of transportations to offer, commuting is still not as easy and as efficient. The transportation system is one of the main problems the country is facing even before the COVID-19 pandemic, and situations worsened as everyone transitioned back to the new normal. According to Abad (2019), the Asian Development Bank (ADB) study reported Metro Manila having the heaviest traffic congestion in the Philippines. Up to this day, much energy and time are consumed in commuting regardless of the distance of one's destination. Besides being hours-long stuck in traffic, train rides were often not spared. Five hundred sixteen Metro Rail Transit (MRT) problems were recorded almost 10 times a week, including offloading accidents in 2017, and almost daily breakdowns in 2018 (Abad, 2019).

However, with the Philippines being highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change due to its location, cycling as a mode of transportation became more practical for its positive effects on both health and the environment. According to Woodcock et al. (2018), increasing the percentage of regular cycling of English citizens from less than 5% to 25% would have a positive environmental impact by reducing passenger transport greenhouse gas emissions by about 2% and decreasing the risk of premature mortality. This data demonstrates that cycling has both an environmental impact and health benefits, supporting the idea that Filipino commuters may find cycling to be a more practical means of transportation.

Furthermore, ever since the pandemic outbreak, many people have turned to riding bicycles after rediscovering the benefits of cycling. In order to promote bicycles as an eco-friendly mode of transportation, the Philippine government declared that every fourth Sunday of November every year would be National Bicycle Day. Miguel (2020) stated that it helped in saving money, exercise, as well as it is essential in reducing pollution and mitigating climate change by decreasing carbon dioxide emissions. In addition to that, the government will be constructing a 600-kilometer bike lane in Metro Manila to ensure the safety of the cyclists, as well as to inspire more individuals to use bicycles.

There are many approaches and perspectives that can be utilized to understand certain behaviors or practices, which subject an individual's whole experience into further exploration. In the context of Filipino cyclists, the Social Practice Theory (SPT) is deemed fit to understand comprehensively the commuting experience of cyclists wherein it will delve deeper into the components that comprise cycling as a social practice. The founders of practice theory movements are notably Anthony Giddens, Pierre Bourdieu, and Bruno Latour, who served as sources of inspirations for contemporary practice theorists, such as Davide Nicolini, Annemarie Mol, Andreas Reckwitz, Theodore Schatzki, Elizabeth Shove, Alan Warde, Robert Schmidt and many others (Weenink & Spaargaren, 2016). Social Practice Theory is described as "a routinized type of behavior which consist of several elements, interconnected to one another: forms of bodily activities, forms of mental activities, 'things' and their use, a background knowledge in the form of understanding, know-how, states of emotion and motivational knowledge" (Weenink & Spaargaren, 2019).

Practices comprise three significant components which are materials like things or technologies; competences such as skills, techniques, or know-how; and meanings as in ideas, symbols, and reasons. Through these components, unique and recognizable links are established as recurring actions are made over time (practices-as-performances), which manifest as common routines (practices-as-

entities) and become social practices within broader bundles of practices.

In the context of this study, the Social Practice Theory was employed to further understand cycling as a practice. Bicycles have been used by Filipinos for different purposes like recreation and running errands and have increasingly been used for commuting to work especially during the pandemic lockdown. Given the status quo of transportation and commuting in the Philippines, the potential of cycling to be a viable mode of transportation has sparked the researchers' interest to explore the experience of current cyclists who use bicycles on main roads to commute to and from work. Using the Social Practice Theory (SPT), the Materials, Meaning, and Competencies that make up cycling as a social practice will be used as a framework in exploring the experience within this practice given the cyclists' purpose in choosing cycling for transportation, the accessibility of bicycles and other materials, the implementation of rules and policies encountered in their environment, and the advantages and disadvantages of using bicycles for commuting. Looking through the three components can help which factors significantly affect the cyclists' commute experience that may encourage or hinder cycling.

Research Questions

This study sought to:

1. Discover the Filipino cyclists' purpose in choosing cycling as their mode of transportation.
2. Explain the Filipino cyclists' view on safety, practicality, accessibility, and implementation of policies.
3. Explore the advantages and disadvantages of using bicycles as a mode of transportation for Filipino cyclists in terms of:
 - 1.1. Safety and Bicycle Maintenance
 - 1.2. Practicality and Accessibility of Cycling in the Philippines
 - 1.3. Implementation of Cycling-Related Policies in the Philippines

Methodology

This research used a qualitative approach through the Phenomenology research design. To achieve these objectives, researchers analyzed the data in an attempt to identify the themes through the lens of Social Practice Theory.

The participants of this research were 10 Filipino adult cyclists, from ages 18 to 59 years old, who are currently living in Metro Manila, and use bicycles at least 8 hours per week as their mode of transportation to and from work. Subjects may be excluded from the study if they are a citizen of any other country besides the Philippines. The participants also have the freedom to volunteer in this study, as well as the right to stop or withdraw from the interview if they start to feel discomfort.

The researchers gathered data through online interviews. Each respondent was catered in separate one-on-one interviews wherein inquiries regarding the research questions were asked. The informed consent was explained to the respondents beforehand. Once the data was collected, it was transcribed by the researchers for data analysis. The researchers followed Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis since it allowed them to uncover emergent themes to understand people's experiences (Wirihana et. al, 2018). Researchers constructed formulated meanings, which were statements that captured the essence of relevant statements, interpreted the data and arranged it through emergent themes.

To establish trustworthiness to the data, triangulation method was established using the theoretical concepts anchored with the variables, interview responses from the participants, and researchers' thematic coding method which were validated by two external assessors. Member checking was also done to validate the respondents' answers and ask for their feedback on the research findings.

Results and Discussion

This study was to explore and understand the commute experience of Filipino cyclists, to know why they choose cycling for transportation, and to assess whether cycling is a viable mode of transportation in Metro Manila. Data is presented according to the study's statements of purpose. The data were gathered through interviews and were treated using Colaizzi's Method of Data Analysis, revealing unique emerging themes that encapsulate the essence of the statements from the respondents.

Table 1. *Emerging Themes Based on the Responses of the Respondents*

Theme	Sub-theme	Illustrative Quote
Positive Synergy of Cycling	Ease of Management	<p>“Katulad nga ng ano, kung gusto nila makatipid ng pamasaha, kung ayaw nila mag ano ng gasolina dahil mahal, maaaring magbike nalang sila para less gastos.”</p> <p>“It adds to my non-exercise activity kasi nga I'm talking about biking through a commuter's perspective. Instead of me taking the jeep or driving, I can find biking two or three kilometers one way, it adds to my non-exercise activity. Whenever I'm commuting, I use that time to clear my thoughts.”</p>
	Health Enhancement	<p>“Nakakapagboost ng magandang pangangatawan, nakakaano ng legs at cardio, sa muscles.”</p> <p>“Nag-iimprove ung mental and physical health mo. Maggogrow ka physically, naeexercise ung paa ganun, mas lalakas ung kain mo, then mas marami kang magiging kaibigan ganyan, mas nakakalabas ka kaysa dati na wala kang bike, nasa bahay ka lang. Sa mental health, nagiging focused ka, concentrated, tapos ano ka, positive ka. Magiging positive ka. Pagka sa</p>

		mental health, mapupush mo sarili mo. For example, mataas ung daan, paahon. Makikita mo ung kasama mo umaahon, gusto mo na rin umahon. Hindi ka susuko agad.”
Uncontrolled External Resources	Environment Refinement	“Siguro ano... promote ng..., to lessen yung ano pollution ng Manila. Hmmm sana maging aware sila sa health benefits.”
	Ineffectiveness of Cycling Related Policies	“Uhm majority cemented and uh ano uh asphalted. Ah since na- most of the time nasa city naman ako, city roads, so manageable naman siya. Uhm kaya lang ga- gaya nga ng sabi ko yung design ng kalsada natin generally speaking hindi pa rin siya people-centric. Uhm like, ang- tignan mo nalang ah, ang mga PWD hindi na nakakagamit ng wheelchair sa mga bangketa natin eh, diba? “
User Managed Internal Resources	Risk Management	“Sobrang init tapos babyahe ka, lalo na kung katanghalian o kainitan. Pero itong mga nakaraan kasi, panghapon ako kaya di na medyo. Pero nung nakaraan kapag maaga ang duty ko. May mga malalaking sasakyan, minsan traffic, may hindi ka magandang ma-eencounter na sumasalubong sa daan.”
	Effective Cycling Facilities Personal Safety Preparations	“Merong dibang bike lanes. Merong mga area na may mga tools at pahangin. Dito sa Manila, may nakita ako na ganun.” “Ay oo naman ho. Unang una kasi may, gumagamit ako ng safety helmet, tapos sumusunod ako sa traffic signs and rules. Hindi ako gumigitna o nakikipagsabayan sa mga malalaking sasakyan, nasa bike lane lamang ako.”

Based on the table above, the data analyzed the overarching sub-themes with three main themes: (1) Positive Synergy of Cycling, (2) Uncontrolled External Resources, and (3) User Managed Internal Resources. These themes represented the major experiences expressed by the respondents in relation to their Commute Experience.

Positive Synergy of Cycling

This theme explored the various positive aspects of cycling according to the respondents’ experiences. Firstly, the respondents highlighted its ease of management, which involved its flexibility, efficiency, practicality, and its easy maintenance. Secondly, the respondents emphasized its health enhancements in terms of both physical and mental health benefits. Lastly, in addition to its health benefits, cyclists also pointed out its environmental refinement which focused on the environmental benefits. These analyses demonstrated that there are also some beneficial sides to the commute experience of Filipino cyclists as they cycle from home to work and vice versa.

In accordance with the theme “Positive Synergy of Cycling” this can be related to the study by Karanikola et. al. (2018), the motivation of commuters to cycle are the additional benefits of improving the cyclists’ general health. Moreover, it reports other positive factors of cycling: less contribution to atmospheric pollution, improvement of social communication, and helps in saving money. Similarly, Filipino cyclists have expressed their satisfaction on how their physical and mental health improved upon cycling to commute in at least a month. Additionally, Ramos (2022) stated many people turned towards cycling since it was budget friendly and safer during the pandemic. Bicycles were also incredibly affordable, especially since it requires little initial investment and the maintenance is also inexpensive, along with the cheap spare parts needed to maintain a bicycle (Bikes & Roll, 2019).

Uncontrolled External Resources

Another theme that emerged entails some challenging aspects of cycling that the respondents experience since there are external factors that are not within the cyclists’ control when commuting on bicycles. First is the ineffectiveness of cycling related policies which included infrastructure issues, and poor implementation of cycling related policies. Secondly, the respondents shared about risk management when cycling which covers weather conditions, and other identified risks relating to road hazards and potential health risks. These findings display the external elements that give cyclists a challenging experience when commuting since some conditions are inevitable and adjustments are made by the cyclists, for instance the warm climate of the Philippines that significantly affects cyclists physically.

Based on the theme, “Uncontrolled External Resources”, there are road policies for cycling that are also as important as those for other vehicles. In terms of the status of the Philippines’ transportation in general, there is a deficit in infrastructure and lack of uniformity in decision-making even despite the initial investments made for such projects (Philippine Development Plan, 2017). The country has been reported to have poor road network quality, lack walkable spaces for pedestrian, and investments for transportation infrastructure is limited (Pagkatotohanan, 2022). With the status quo of transportation in the country, cyclists can indeed be affected in terms of ineffective implementations of policies and lack of infrastructure that put their safety at risk. The infrastructure for commuters and public transport vehicles that occupy the majority of the road are lacking, and bicycles that endure the battle in congested roads may be taking even less space and attention than they need for safer cycling. Additionally, around 87% of Filipinos agreed that “Roads in the Philippine cities and municipalities will be better off if public transportation, bicycles and pedestrians are given priority over private vehicles” when a survey from Social Weather Stations (SWS) was conducted (Department of Health, 2021).

User Managed Internal Resources

The last theme presents the aspects that can contribute positively to the cyclists’ experience in terms of factors that are within their

control and those that are readily available. First, having effective cycling facilities which include accessible bike lanes, and accessible bike parking. Next is personal safety and preparations that cyclists must practice which are mental preparedness, and physical preparedness.

In accordance with the “User Managed Internal Resources” theme, the Philippines’ Department of Transportation (DOTr) mentioned that existing bike lanes were aimed to be extended and construct another 234 kilometers of bike lanes across eight regions. Currently, the country has 564 kilometers of bike lanes nationwide, with Metro Manila Bike Lane Network having 313 kilometers (Bautista, 2022). Former senator Miriam Defensor Santiago introduced the "Bike-Friendly Communities Act," which focuses on encouraging citizens to use bicycles as an alternative mode of transportation by establishing a National Bike Program that includes the construction and maintenance of bicycle lanes, parking, and support facilities (Senate of the Philippines, 2011).

Figure 1. *Research Simulacrum*

This figure represents the integrated themes of the commute experience of Filipino cyclists in Metro Manila. The front wheel symbolizes the Positive Synergy of Cycling, highlighting the sub themes Ease of Management and Health and Environment Enhancement. This theme was set at the front since it can be influential in converting commuters to cyclists. Some participants believe that commuters have their own choices, and that cycling is not for everybody but nonetheless, they believe that the pros of cycling far outweigh its cons.

Then, the rear end wheel represents the Uncontrolled External Resources, highlighting the Ineffectiveness of Cycling-Related Policies and Risk Management. This theme was set at the back since the respondents claim that the Cycling-Related Policies in the country is lagging behind. For instance, a participant stated that there are infrastructures available for cyclists but are, however, lacking. Some participant also believes that bike lanes can be improved by having the government authorities learn "people-centric urban planning" first since most roads and infrastructures are not yet designed for inclusivity.

The basket contains the User Managed Internal Resources, highlighting the Cycling Essentials, Effective Cycling Facilities, and Personal Safety Preparations. This theme was strategically placed in the front of the cyclist's seat because according to the participants, it is the only theme that the cyclist can easily control.

Conclusion

From the collected data, the researchers conclude that:

The Filipino cyclists choose cycling as their mode of transportation because of its flexibility, efficiency, practicality, easy maintenance, and benefits on health and environment. These findings suggest that Filipino cyclists get a thrill out of a simple and worry-free mode of transportation because it provides an uncomplicated commute experience.

Filipino cyclists view their commute experience as a positive synergy especially for its practicality and its aid in health enhancement

and environment refinement. These results imply that Filipino cyclists take the pleasure in making cycling a social practice, since their view on its safety, practicality, and accessibility is positively harmonious.

The advantages of cycling as a mode of transportation are the ease of management and the user managed internal resources. These results hold implications for the promising factors that reward the cyclist when cycling is made a social practice.

On the other hand, the disadvantages are the uncontrolled external resources including the ineffectiveness of cycling related policies and poor risk management. This suggests that the cycling related policies in the Philippines are disregarded and must be improved in the same way policies for private and public vehicles are pursued on by the government agencies responsible for this matter.

The researchers would recommend future researchers to use a wider range of locations in finding respondents and gathering data to have a bigger sample size. Moreover, the motivations of recent cyclists and those of more experienced cyclists can be compared and considered too. The idea of whether the length of a cyclist's experience can also be considered if it is a contributing factor to their views on safety, accessibility, and practicality in using bicycles as a mode of transportation.

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